

Annual Methodological Archive Research Review

<http://amresearchreview.com/index.php/Journal/about>

Polymeric Synthesis of Metallic Oxide Nanocomposite in the Presence of Rare Earth for their Water-Splitting Applications

¹Aqsa Ayyoub, ²Prof. Dr. Zahida Batool

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Aqsa Ayyoub

Department of Physics - The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan,
Corresponding Author, aqsa14099@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Zahida Batool

Department of Physics - The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan,
zahida.batool@iub.edu.pk

The production of hydrogen and oxygen from water, driven by solar energy through photoelectrochemical and electrocatalysis processes, represents a promising avenue toward clean fuel generation. This study focuses on the synthesis and comprehensive characterization of Bismuth oxide-based nanocomposites, specifically Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP, using the Sol-gel method. To evaluate the synthesized nanocomposites, a diverse array of characterization techniques were employed, including X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), cyclic voltammetry (CV), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The XRD patterns confirmed the formation of Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP nanocomposites, exhibiting a cubic crystalline structure. Crystallite size and lattice strain were meticulously determined using the Scherrer formula, Williamson-Hall, and Scherrer plot methods, revealing average crystallite sizes of 15.41 nm, 13.64 nm, and 15.01 nm, respectively. SEM was used to determine the surface morphology and particle distribution. Furthermore, cyclic voltammetry was employed to ascertain the electrochemical performance of the Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP nanocomposites. Our findings indicate that Sol-gel synthesized Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂ and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP composites exhibit promising characteristics for water splitting applications. Through extensive electrochemical testing, including CV, LSV, and EIS, we observed that these prepared nanocomposites exhibit higher current densities of 10 mAcm⁻² at significantly lower over potential (190 mV and 25.7 mV vs RHE) and smaller Tafel slopes (88.3 mVdec⁻¹ and 261 mVdec⁻¹) in the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) compared to other composite materials. Additionally, electrochemical impedance measurements indicated that the resistance of the modified electrode and the bare electrode ranged from 0 to 160 Ω. These results collectively demonstrate the promising potential of Bi₂O₃/NiO-based nanocomposites as efficient catalysts for sustainable water-splitting processes.

INTRODUCTION

There are many common issues all around the world. Among these issues, a few issues are very important. These are energy production and storage and environmental pollution. Researchers are continuously working their efforts to address these issues. The use of fossil fuels for energy production and preservation is one solution to energy shortages that has gained widespread recognition (Chaudhary, Basha et al. 2023). On the other hand, when fossil fuels are burned, they give off harmful gases that contribute directly to pollution and, in the long run, global warming (Yue, Lambert et al. 2021). Because of this, it is crucial to phase out fossil fuels in favor of renewable energy sources that are better for the environment (Tahir, Chaudhary et al. 2022). Hydrogen is a great choice for making energy in the future because it is light and has a high energy density (Yousaf, Katubi et al. 2023). Hydrogen can be made in several different ways, such as by electrolyzing or photolyzing water, reforming biomass, or burning fossil fuels (Hassan, Baig et al. 2023). Most hydrogen is made through a process called electrolysis (Osgood, Devaguptapu et al. 2016). In electrochemical water-splitting reactions, at the cathode, the HER takes while the OER takes place at the anode. Among the issues, electrocatalytic water-splitting has drawn a lot of interest due to its inexpensive, high efficiency, and low power threshold.

Since the OER has slow rate kinetics and requires a high energy barrier to generate the reaction, it needs a very large overpotential and is inefficient (Wang, Lu et al. 2021). The HER process has been observed to have a faster rate of kinetics and require very low overpotential (Stühmeier, Pietsch et al. 2021). Materials based on noble metals, such as ruthenium and iridium oxides for the oxygen evolution reaction and platinum for the hydrogen evolution reaction, exhibit impressive water-splitting efficiency, but they are not practical for widespread use due to their scarcity, high cost, and short longevity (Liu, Ma et al. 2021). Therefore, in the last few decades, there has been a lot of focus on developing and manufacturing electrocatalysts that are highly efficient, extremely accessible, and very cheap for high-efficiency water splitting. In particular, oxides, chalcogenides, phosphides, and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) based on transition metals have gained popularity due to their superior performances and extended durability (Liu, Guo et al. 2023). Since the above-discussed state-of-the-art electrocatalysts only show performance in one of these areas, it is both difficult and exciting to design a dual functional catalyst that can concurrently catalyze both hydrogen evolution and oxygen evolution reactions.

Among the compounds, Bi_2O_3 has attracted significant interest due to its unique crystal structures with various probable modifications and band gaps in the desired range (Wang, Paik

et al. 2015). Bi_2O_3 mainly has four polymorphs, including the monoclinic (α), tetragonal (β), body-centered cubic (γ), and face-centered (δ) phases. Among these, narrow band gaps of 2.8 and 2.48 eV for α - Bi_2O_3 and β - Bi_2O_3 , respectively, have been reported in most experimental studies out of which β - Bi_2O_3 has been well known to exhibit superior photocatalytic activity under visible light illumination (Li, Li et al. 2014).

The nickel oxide hydroxide ($\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})$) as an electrocatalyst for water splitting has also received significant attention due to its material potential. There is a lot of surface area available for electrocatalytic reactions on $\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})$ because of its layered structure. Their electrocatalytic activity and efficiency for water-splitting reactions, especially the OER, are improved as a result of the layered structure. The OER reaction is an essential part of the water-splitting reaction, but it is a difficult reaction that calls for a lot of overpotentials to be active. $\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})$ are easy to synthesize, abundant, and inexpensive, making them preferable over electrocatalysts based on precious metals like platinum for use in large-scale applications. $\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})$ activity for the HER is comparable to that of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{NiO}(\text{OH})$, but lower than that of some other electrocatalysts [29,30]. Researchers have attempted a variety of methods, including doping with other metals and integrating them into composite materials with other materials like carbon nanotubes (CNTs), to increase their activity for HER (Afaq, BaQais et al. 2024).

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS

Bismuth nitrate pentahydrate, nickel nitrate pentahydrate, cerium nitrate hexahydrate, and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) were used to synthesize the nanocomposite, NaOH as a pH-controlling agent, and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as a solvent. Sigma Aldrich provided the materials and chemicals used in the synthesis technique. Throughout the trial, distilled water and ethanol were utilized for washing purposes.

TABLE 1: DETAILS OF CHEMICAL USED IN NANOCOMPOSITE SYNTHESIS

Sr. No.	Chemicals	Chemical formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)
1	Bismuth nitrate pentahydrate	$\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	485.07
2	Nickel nitrate pentahydrate	$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	290.80
3	Cerium nitrate hexahydrate	$\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	434.22
4	Polyvinylpyrrolidone	PVP	111.14

5	Dimethyl sulfoxide	C_2H_6OS	78.13
6	Ethanol	$C_2 H_6 O$	46.07
7	Sodium hydroxide	$NaOH$	39.997

SYNTHESIS OF Bi_2O_3/NiO COMPOSITE

2.6 grams of bismuth nitrate pent hydrate has been added to a 100 ml beaker containing 30 ml DMSO to create a Bi_2O_3/NiO nanocomposite. Placing the beaker on a hot plate, start stirring with a magnetic stirrer, and then take the beaker off the hot plate after around two hours. To maintain pressure on the beaker, aluminum foil was being employed. Until all of the $Bi(NO_3)_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ has been dissolved, the solution is continuously stirred. Finally, a pale golden hue was achieved (Jiang and Wang 2016) . After that, a 100 ml beaker containing 30 ml of DMSO was filled with 0.42g of nickel nitrate pentahydrate. With the beaker on a hot plate, start stirring for around two hours at an ambient temperature of 70 °C using a magnetic stirrer. Sodium hydroxide, also known as NaOH, helped 2.6 g of Bismuth nitrate 30 ml DMSO Bi_2O_3 NPs Wash and dried at 50°C Heated at 300°C in oven Heated at 70°C Figure 4. 1: Flow chart of Bi_2O_3 37 to maintain the PH. Until all of the $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$ has been completely dissipated in the solution, the solution is continuously stirred. Finally, the color black was attained. Now for making nanocomposites of Bi_2O_3/NiO , materials were dignified in Molar ratio (0.19M). Bismuth oxide and Nickel oxide powder was dissolved in 30 ml of DMSO separately. For an hour, the solution was agitated. Mix the nickel oxide and bismuth oxide solutions after an hour of stirring. Sodium hydroxide was employed to keep the pH between 9 and 10. The mixture was 0.42 g of Nickel nitrate 30 ml DMSO Heated at 70°C NiO_2 NPs Wash and dried at 50°C Heated at 300°C in oven Figure 4. 3: Flow chart of NiO 38 stirred continuously to keep the temperature around 70 degrees Celsius. The precipitates were cooked in an oven at 180°C for two hours. Finally, a colored composite was produced.

SYNTHESIS OF $Bi_2O_3/NiO/CeO_2$ NANOCOMPOSITE

0.5 g of cerium nitrate hexahydrate was added to a 100 ml beaker with 10 ml of DMSO to create the $Bi_2O_3/NiO/CeO_2$ nanocomposite. Using a magnetic stirrer and a temperature of 50°C, place the beaker on a hot plate and start stirring. Sodium hydroxide was used to keep the PH constant. The mixture is continuously stirred until all of the $Ce(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ has been dissolved. The precipitate was cooked in a furnace for two hours at 650 degrees Celsius. Finally, a rust-brown hue was achieved. Now, the components were determined in molar ratios to construct the nanocomposite of Bi_2O_3 , NiO, and CeO_2 . Separately, 30 ml of DMSO was used to dissolve cerium

oxide, bismuth oxide solution, and nickel oxide solution. For an hour, the solution was agitated. Mix the composite of nickel oxide, bismuth oxide, and cerium oxide after one hour of stirring. Sodium hydroxide was employed to keep the pH between 9 and 10. The mixture was stirred continuously to keep the temperature at 50°C. The precipitates were cooked in an oven at 180°C for two hours. Finally, a composite in the color black was produced.

SYNTHESIS OF Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP COMPOSITE

Now, the solution of PVP (0.1g) within 20ml comprising dimethyl sulfoxide was added dropwise to the Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂ solution to form the nanocomposite of Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP. For an hour, the solution was agitated. Sodium hydroxide was employed to keep the pH between 9 and 10. The mixture was stirred continuously to keep the temperature around 90 degrees Celsius. The precipitates were cooked for two hours at 180 degrees Celsius in the oven. Finally, a black nanocomposite was produced.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD ANALYSIS

Phase identification and crystal structure of the Bi₂O₃, NiO, CeO₂, Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP nanocomposites were investigated using an X-ray diffractometer with a range of 10° to 70° and CuKα radiations [1.5406 Å]. The XRD data was examined using the Origin Pro. To investigate the NPs' hidden properties, many peaks were found and joined. Also utilizing the origin software, the peaks were labeled and marked. Once the structure of the synthesized substance was confirmed, the obtained data was compared with the peaks on the JCPDS card.

The average crystalline size of synthesized samples was calculated using Debye Sherrer's formula applied to a few notable peaks (Imran, Batool et al. 2022).

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \rightarrow (4.1)$$

Where the following elements are taken into account:

D= which stands for the crystal's size;

K= which represents the crystallite form factor with a defined value of 0.9; which stands for the CuKα radiation's wavelength;

β= which stands for the full width at half maximum (measured in radians; and, which stands for the angle of diffraction. The interplanar gap is calculated using Bragg's formula:

$$d = \lambda / (2\sin\theta)$$

In this case, the letters d stand for the interplanar distance, for an incident X-ray wavelength, & for the Bragg's angle. Additionally, the following formula can be used to calculate dislocation density:

$$\text{Dislocation density} = \frac{1}{D^2}$$

The variable D from the aforementioned equation stands for the crystal size. Using XRD data, this equation is used to determine the microstrain. The related Miller indices, FWHM, size of crystal, density of dislocation, & interplanar spacing of each sample are shown in the table that follows.

We use the following formula, the amount of stress may be determined:

$$\text{stress} = \frac{FWHM}{\tan\theta} \rightarrow (4.5)$$

To determine micro strain, apply the following relationship:

$$\text{Micro strain} = \frac{D \tan\theta}{4} \rightarrow (4.6)$$

Calculating the width of Bragg's peaks involves integrating sample impacts and measurements.

$$\beta_{hkl} = \beta^2 \text{ measured} + \beta^2 \text{ instrumental} \rightarrow (4.8)$$

Hence,

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{B \cos\theta} \rightarrow \cos\theta = \frac{K\lambda}{D(\frac{1}{\beta})} \rightarrow (4.9)$$

An S.P has been drawn across $1/\beta$ and $\cos\theta$, as seen in Fig. 4.10, with $1/\beta$ along the x-axis & $\cos\theta$ along the y-axis. Data were linearly fitted, and the slope of the fitted line was used to determine the crystallite size.

FIGURE 1: XRD PATTERN OF BI₂O₃, NIO, CEO₂, BI₂O₃/NIO, BI₂O₃/NIO/CEO₂, AND BI₂O₃/NIO/CEO₂/PVP NANOCOMPOSITES

SEM ANALYSIS

SEM ANALYSIS OF BI₂O₃ NANOPARTICLES

Results of the SEM investigation of the Bi₂O₃ nanocomposite. The Bi₂O₃ was produced as a lump of spherical particles (Chen, Hosseini et al. 2019).

SEM ANALYSIS OF NIO NANOPARTICLES

SEM images were used to analyze the surface morphology of NiO nanoparticles. The NiO SEM picture is seen in Figure. The items are small and collected, as can be observed, Spherical-shaped nanoparticles (Salavati-Niasari, Mir et al. 2010).

SEM ANALYSIS OF CEO₂ NANOPARTICLES

Using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), nanoparticle morphology is discovered. In Figure

4.30, the SEM picture of the freshly generated cerium dioxide nanoparticles is shown. In the image, it can be observed that the bulk of particles are spherical. However, some of the elongated particles are also seen to be agglomerated (Kumar, Selvarajan et al. 2010).

SEM ANALYSIS OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ NANOCOMPOSITES

The morphology of artificial $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ nanocomposites was studied using SEM. The Bi_2O_3 was made from a mass of spherical particles at a magnification of 10.00K. For NiO, this image shows the particles are small and gathered into spherical nanoparticles. This demonstrates the presence of Bi_2O_3 and NiO in our nanocomposite.

SEM ANALYSIS OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ NANOCOMPOSITES

The morphology of artificial $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ nanocomposites was studied using SEM. The Bi_2O_3 was made from a mass of spherical particles at a magnification of 10.00K. For NiO, this image shows the particles are small and gathered into spherical nanoparticles. For CeO_2 , the majority of the particles are spherical, as can be seen in Figure 4.32. But it's also noticeable that certain of the extended particles have gathered together.

SEM ANALYSIS OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ /PVP

Nanocomposites the morphology of artificial $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ /PVP nanocomposites was studied using SEM. The Bi_2O_3 was made from a mass of spherical particles at a magnification of 10.00K. For NiO, this image shows the particles are small and gathered into spherical nanoparticles. For CeO_2 , the majority of the particles are spherical. But it's also noticeable that certain of the extended particles have gathered together. The composite's morphology is altered by a polymer.

FIGURE 2: SEM IMAGE OF (A) Bi_2O_3 (B) NiO (C) CeO_2 (D) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ (E) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ (F) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$

FTIR ANALYSIS

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) is the most widely recognized type of infrared spectroscopy. The fundamental principle of all infrared spectroscopies is that when infrared energy traverses a substance, it is absorbed. The observation of which radiation reaches the sample is duly recorded. The resultant spectrum comprises numerous peaks that can be visually perceived by humans. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy is used to examine $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ made using the Sol-gel process. We measured the IR spectra of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ at wavelengths between 4000 and 500 cm^{-1} . The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) plot visually represents the stretching or transmittance region, along with the identification of functional groups, within various materials. Figure (a) shows that the bismuth oxide nanoparticle's FTIR absorption spectrum was measured in the 500–4000 cm^{-1} range. At 3421 cm^{-1} , the O-H stretching vibrations may be seen. The metal-oxygen (Bi-O) bonding is the cause of the peak at 435-505 cm^{-1} . C-C stretching's vibration mode has a 1406 cm^{-1} designated wavelength (Nurmalasari, Yulizar et al. 2020). Figure 4.26 (b) Ce-O stretching was identified by the bands seen at 489 cm^{-1} . The bands seen at 1620 cm^{-1} could be the result of the bending vibrational mode of H-O-H brought on by the air's absorption of water. O-H stretching was used to explain the bands seen at 3200-3500 cm^{-1} . The bands seen at 1015 cm^{-1} might be caused by C-O stretching vibration from more CO_2 that could be absorbed at the surface of CeO_2 (Yadav, Ansari et al. 2023). Figure 4.26 (c) OH group stretching vibrations are responsible for the, 3641 cm^{-1} , 3609 cm^{-1} , and 3137 cm^{-1} peaks. The H_2O molecule's deformation vibration is responsible for the vibrational band at 1624 cm^{-1} . At 1403 cm^{-1} , the band attributed to C=O's asymmetries is visible. Ni-O bond is linked to the peak at 523 cm^{-1} (Anitha, Suganya et al. 2018).

FIGURE 3: SHOWS THAT THE FTIR SPECTRA (A) Bi_2O_3 (B) NiO (C) CeO_2 (D) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ (E) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$ (F) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ NANOCOMPOSITE ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

The size of the inhibitory zone (mm) for each bacterium was measured after 24 hours. Using a ruler, the zones of inhibition were measured. The results demonstrated that the pseudomonas and staphylococcus growth was inhibited by the Bi_2O_3 , NiO , CeO_2 , $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, and $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ samples in the table. For Pseudomonas and Staphylococcus, the computed maximum zones of inhibition were 20mm, 23mm, 20mm, 20mm, 24mm, and 26 mm, respectively. The literature states that a material has excellent antibacterial qualities if its ZOI diameter is greater than 6mm and no antimicrobial properties if it is less than 6mm. Gram-negative bacteria are less resilient to physical disturbances than gram-positive bacteria. A polymer enhances the antibacterial abilities of nanoparticles. The effect of bacterial cell walls on particle interaction is minimal when concentrations are low; however, the quantity of nanoparticles or nanocomposites significantly affects antibacterial activity. Conversely, when concentrations are high, particle aggregation increases, resulting in a decrease in the surface-to-

volume ratio and a reduction in the extent of interaction between the particle and the bacterial cell walls (Imran, Batool et al. 2022).

FIGURE 4: SHOWS CLEAR DIFFERENCE OF INHIBITION ZONE OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, AND $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ AGAINST PSEUDOMONAS BY INCREASING THE CONCENTRATION OF THE SAMPLE

FIGURE 5: SHOWS CLEAR DIFFERENCE OF INHIBITION ZONE OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, AND $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ AGAINST STAPHYLOCOCCUS BY INCREASING THE CONCENTRATION OF THE SAMPLE

WATER SPLITTING

ELECTROCATALYTIC OER AND HER PERFORMANCES

Since OER is a complicated and energy-intensive four-electron transfer process that involves O-H bond breaking and O=O bond creation, we first look into the electrocatalysts' OER activity. The catalysts were applied to the carbon fiber paper (CFP) with an exact mass-loading (2.2 mg

cm²), and the outcome was assessed in an ordinary three-electrode setup with an alkaline 1 M KOH solution (Ashwani and Sayan 2017).

Performance OER in alkaline or acidic environments (M is the electro-catalyst surface, while OH*, OOH*, and O* species operate as intermediates) and the following equations:

By using the LSV test at a sweeping rate of 10 mVs⁻¹ and automated iR correction, the OER activity of the samples of Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP was evaluated. As a result of the OER run, the LSV curves of Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP are shown in Figure 6. A detailed evaluation of the electrocatalysts' performance was also carried out to identify the catalyst that produced the 10 mAcm⁻² current density that was observed. At a current density of 10mAcm⁻², the measured the overpotential for Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP, respectively, was 265mV, 203mV, and 190mV. Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP has a lower overpotential value than the other samples, which indicates superior OER performance. It has been reported that PVP acts as a surface stabilizer and growth modifier which helps in reducing the particle size that ultimately increases the surface area and catalytic activity (Dalai, Dash et al. 2022).

FIGURE 6: LSV POLARIZATION OF BI₂O₃/NIO, BI₂O₃/NIO/CEO₂, AND BI₂O₃/NIO/CEO₂/PVP NANOCOMPOSITE

Tafel slopes for Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP samples are 67.9, 45.2, 88.3 mVdec⁻¹, respectively. The smallest Tafel slope value of the Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂ electrocatalysts reflects the improved electrocatalytic behavior and excellent kinetics toward OER. Tafel plots, in addition, were employed to ascertain the mechanism of the Oxygen Evolution Reaction transpiring at the surface of the electrode.

FIGURE 7: TAFEL SLOPE OF OER OF BI₂O₃/NIO/CEO₂/PVP NANOCOMPOSITE

To assess the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) activity of the samples under investigation, the HER polarization curves of Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP were compared to those of state-of-the-art platinum (Pt) foil. Figure (a) presents the HER profiles of Pt, Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP. The electrochemical performance of the prepared material was evaluated by measuring the overpotential. The observed overpotential for Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP were determined to be 73mV, 59mV, and 25.7mV, respectively, at a current density of 10mAcm⁻² in hydrogen evolution experiments. Notably, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP exhibited a lower overpotential value compared to the other samples, suggesting its superior performance in the HER process. Recently, it has been reported that the utilization of Pt as the counter electrode for HER may lead to the dissolution of Pt in the electrolytes and subsequent transfer onto the working electrode, thereby supporting the HER activity.

LSV data was utilized to determine the Tafel slopes. The Tafel slope values were observed to be 282 mVdec⁻¹ for Bi₂O₃/NiO, 424 mVdec⁻¹ for Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and 261mVdec⁻¹ for Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP. The Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP exhibited the smallest Tafel slope, indicating commendable reaction kinetics and electron transfer efficiency in the hydrogen

evolution reaction (HER).

FIGURE 8: LSV POLARIZATION OF HER OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, AND $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ NANOCOMPOSITE

CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY (CV)

I inserted the functioning electrode into the electrolyte solution and subsequently activated the system, thereby allowing the passage of electrical current through the electrode. As the current traversed the electrode, it generated a visual representation of the voltammogram on the computer screen. To observe the effects of varying scan rates, namely 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 mV/s, I conducted this experiment. It was evident that the area encompassed by the voltammogram increased proportionally with the escalation of the scan rate. Consequently, I plotted the CV curves of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, and $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ nanocomposites, employing the potential vs RHE on the x-axis and current density on the y-axis, at different scan rates. To determine the current density the following formula is used. *Current density (J) = Curr(I) Area(A)* (4.33) To find the potential over RHE following formula is used; $ERHE = E_{measured} + E_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.059 * pH$. Where, E (Ag/AgCl) = observed potential Ag/AgCl = reference electrode.

FIGURE 9: CV CURVES OF $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ NANOCOMPOSITE SAMPLE WITH INCREASING SCAN RATE FROM 20 TO 100 MV/S IN 1.0 M KOH ANALYZING THE ELECTROCHEMICAL SURFACE AREA (ECSA)

The cyclic voltammogram of the fabricated $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, and $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ materials was recorded for the non-faradic region at various scan rates (mVs^{-1}). The relationship between scan rate and current (A) was utilized to calculate the electrochemical surface area (ECSA) of the resulting samples, which is shown in Figure 5. The slope of these linear plots was considered as the double-layer capacitance (Cdl). The average Cdl values of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$, $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2$, and $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ were determined to be 69, 2.35, and 4.6 mFcm^{-2} , respectively. The higher average Cdl values of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ indicate a larger electroactive surface area for improved electrochemical performance. To find the electrochemical Surface area (ECSA) formula $\text{ECSA} = \frac{C_{dl}}{C_s}$. Where C_s is the specific capacitance of the working electrode which is nickel foam and its specific capacitance is 40 $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ in 1M of KOH solution. Furthermore, the binary nanocomposite has greater available ECSA (1.725) as compared to its counterpart, which means it provides a highly porous shape and more exposed electroactive sites, which are responsible for excellent OER and HER performances.

FIGURE 10: GRAPH OF SYNTHESIZED $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ NANOCOMPOSITE FOR DETERMINING ECSA

ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY (EIS)

For electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, an initial step involved the preparation of a 1M potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution. Subsequently, the working electrode was immersed into the aforementioned solution, and the system was activated by applying a potential window of approximately 0.5 V. The impedance graph of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ reveals that the commencement of the semicircular curve indicates the presence of unbounded charged particles, thereby signifying a reduced resistance against the unrestricted motion of these charged particles. The impedance graph of my sample $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ nanocomposite its superior conductivity and efficient charge transfer. For $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}/\text{CeO}_2/\text{PVP}$ nanocomposite the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) value is 104.18 Ω .

FIGURE 11: EIS PLOT OF Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP NANOCOMPOSITE

CONCLUSION

In this research, theranostic agents and multifunctional nanoparticles composed of pure Bi₂O₃, Bi₂O₃/NiO, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂, and Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP were synthesized using the Sol-gel method. Various characterization techniques, including X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), were employed to analyze these synthesized nanocomposites. The XRD patterns confirm that the fabricated samples exhibit a cubic crystalline structure. The average crystallite size was determined using the Scherrer formula for Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP, resulting in a crystallite size of 15.01 nm with a dislocation density of 0.00544 m⁻². The FTIR spectra revealed absorption peaks corresponding to the Bi–O, Ni–O bond, and Ce–O bond, occurring in the range of 435–505 cm⁻¹, 523 cm⁻¹, and 489 cm⁻¹, respectively, representing stretching vibrations. SEM analysis confirmed that the bismuth oxide particles were spherical, cerium oxide was agglomerated, and nickel oxide particles were relatively small in the nanocomposites of Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP. These optimized nanocomposites, Bi₂O₃/NiO/CeO₂/PVP, demonstrated their potential as universal water-splitting electrocatalysts, performing both Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) and Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) efficiently.

Extensive electrochemical tests, including CV, LSV, and EIS, revealed that these prepared nanocomposites exhibited higher current densities (10 mAcm^{-2}) at significantly lower overpotential (190 mV and 25.7 mV vs RHE) and smaller Tafel slopes (88.3 mVdec^{-1} and 261 mVdec^{-1}) in the OER and HER compared to other composite materials. Furthermore, electrochemical impedance measurements indicated that the resistance of the modified electrode and the bare electrode ranged from 0 to 160Ω . These results collectively emphasize the promising potential of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiO}$ -based nanocomposites as effective catalysts for sustainable water-splitting processes. Our work was focused on creating a highly stable and electrocatalytically active catalyst to enhance water splitting in an alkaline medium, using a straight forward and cost-effective method that can be readily scaled for larger production volumes."

REFERENCES

- Afaq, M., BaQais, A., et al. (2024). Fabrication of $\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_3(\text{OH})/\text{CNTs}$ -based electrocatalyst for efficient bifunctional electrocatalytic water splitting. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 60, 601–610.
- Anitha, S., Suganya, M., et al. (2018). Synthesis and characterization of NiO-CdO composite materials towards photoconductive and antibacterial applications. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 211, 88–96.
- Ashwani, K., & Sayan, B. (2017). Porous NiFe -oxide nanocubes as bifunctional electrocatalysts for efficient water-splitting.
- Chaudhary, K., Basha, B., et al. (2023). 3D cellular lattice-like Ti_3C_2 MXene-based aerogels embedded with metal selenides particles for energy storage and water splitting applications. *Fuel*, 351, 128856.
- Chen, L., Hosseini, M., et al. (2019). Synthesis and characterization of $\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3-\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ nanocomposites: Photocatalytic, quenching, repeatability, and antibacterial performances. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 30, 13067–13075.
- Dalai, N., Dash, B., et al. (2022). Bifunctional activity of PVP K-30 assisted cobalt molybdate for electrocatalytic water splitting. *ChemistrySelect*, 7(36), e202202270.
- Hassan, M., Baig, M. M., et al. (2023). Efficient water splitting catalyst: Low-temperature selenization of Co and Ni hydroxide nanosheets on carbon cloth for enhanced electrocatalytic activity. *Diamond and Related Materials*, 139, 110298.

- Imran, R., Batool, Z., et al. (2022). In vivo toxicity and antibacterial assessment of Bi₂Se₃/GO/PVA nanocomposite synthesized via hydrothermal route. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 290, 126535.
- Jiang, Z., & Wang, Y. (2016). Preparation of porous bismuth oxide by sol-gel method using citric acid. *Material Science and Environmental Engineering*.
- Kumar, E., Selvarajan, P., et al. (2010). Preparation and studies of cerium dioxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles by microwave-assisted solution method. *Recent Research in Science and Technology*, 2(4).
- Li, M., Li, F., et al. (2014). Tailoring the band structure of β-Bi₂O₃ by co-doping for realized photocatalytic hydrogen generation. *Chemical Physics Letters*, 601, 92–97.
- Liu, J., Ma, J., et al. (2021). 2021 roadmap: Electrocatalysts for green catalytic processes. *Journal of Physics: Materials*, 4(2), 022004.
- Liu, Y., Guo, Y., et al. (2023). A mini review on transition metal chalcogenides for electrocatalytic water splitting: Bridging material design and practical application. *Energy & Fuels*, 37(4), 2608–2630.
- Nurmalasari, N., Yulizar, Y., et al. (2020). Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles: Synthesis, characterizations, and photocatalytic activity. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*: IOP Publishing.
- Osgood, H., Devaguptapu, S. V., et al. (2016). Transition metal (Fe, Co, Ni, and Mn) oxides for oxygen reduction and evolution bifunctional catalysts in alkaline media. *Nano Today*, 11(5), 601–625.
- Salavati-Niasari, M., Mir, N., et al. (2010). A novel precursor in preparation and characterization of nickel oxide nanoparticles via thermal decomposition approach. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 493(1–2), 163–168.
- Stühmeier, B. M., Pietsch, M. R., et al. (2021). Pressure and temperature dependence of the hydrogen oxidation and evolution reaction kinetics on Pt electrocatalysts via PEMFC-based hydrogen-pump measurements. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 168(6), 064516.

- Tahir, T., Chaudhary, K., et al. (2022). Synthesis of sponge-like Gd^{3+} doped vanadium oxide/2D MXene composites for improved degradation of industrial effluents and pathogens. *Ceramics International*, 48(2), 1969–1980.
- Wang, F., Paik, J. K., et al. (2015). Ultimate shear strength of intact and cracked stiffened panels. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 88, 48–57.
- Wang, S., Lu, A., et al. (2021). Hydrogen production from water electrolysis: Role of catalysts. *Nano Convergence*, 8(1), 4.
- Yadav, I. D., Ansari, A., et al. (2023). Facile synthesis of CeO_2 nanoparticles and their applications in photodegradation of methylene blue and as supercapacitor electrode material. *Bulletin of Materials Science*, 46(2), 86.
- Yousaf, S., Katubi, K. M., et al. (2023). Modulating electronic and structural properties of NiCo-layered double hydroxide with iodine: As an efficient electro-catalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 48(70), 27201–27214.
- Yue, M., Lambert, H., et al. (2021). Hydrogen energy systems: A critical review of technologies, applications, trends and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 146, 111180.